

Pawo of Pemakö

Date of recording: 21/01/2013.

Location of recording: Yortong village, Singa circle, Upper Siang district, Arunachal Pradesh, India.

Participants: Tshewang Lhazom (tshe-dbañ lha-ḥdzoms/female/77 years at time of recording, Khampa Tibetan, born in Payingdem village, residence in Singa village). Other unknown local participants, including the main male patient and the lady in the black coat who acts as the interpreter of the *dpah-bo*'s diagnosis.

Languages: Chöke, Pemakö Tshangla, Khampa Tibetan.

Short description:

This is a healing rite by the *dbah-bo* (although this is a male term, she is not referred to by the female form *dpah-mo*, although she is referred to with the female term *jo-mo* by the Tshangla speakers of the area) Tshewang Lhazom. She is a Khampa Tibetan lady who becomes ritually possessed by an unidentified deity and then obtains curative powers, both in identifying the cause of illness as well as curing it. In this case, the patient is suffering from leg pain. After the initial sequence (PAWO210113AV, PAWO210113BV), and the moment of possession (PAWO210113CV), the complaints of the patient are explained and the *dpah-bo* gives her diagnosis (PAWO210113DV), after which various offerings are made (PAWO210113EV), and the *dpah-bo* expels curative phlegm (PAWO210113FV). She then pastes this phlegm mixed with butter on the head of the patient and uses a broom made of a medicinal plant to splash boiling hot water from a cauldron in which three round rocks (a black one, a white one, and a multicoloured one) brought from the river bed near the pilgrimage site of Dewakota that were heated in the fire are placed (PAWO210113GV, PAWO210113HV). Other people suffering from some illness are also treated. She then provides further advice regarding cure (PAWO210113IV), and then concludes the session (PAWO210113JV, PAWO210113KV, PAWO210113LV, PAWO210113MV).

By late 2017, this *dpah-bo* was still alive and practicing.

Accompanying video files:

<i>file name</i>	<i>file size (MB)</i>	<i>file duration (hh:mm:ss)</i>	<i>file type</i>
PAWO210113AV	78.7	00:01:41	.mts
PAWO210113BV	188	00:03:46	.mts
PAWO210113CV	308	00:06:03	.mts
PAWO210113DV	122	00:02:30	.mts
PAWO210113EV	106	00:02:12	.mts
PAWO210113FV	62.4	00:01:18	.mts
PAWO210113GV	175	00:03:31	.mts
PAWO210113HV	33.1	00:00:43	.mts
PAWO210113IV	243	00:04:49	.mts
PAWO210113JV	31.4	00:00:45	.mts
PAWO210113KV	19.4	00:00:24	.mts
PAWO210113LV	12.2	00:00:16	.mts
PAWO210113MV	44.2	00:01:01	.mts

Accompanying photo files:

2 in total.

DOI's of latest version of accompanying files:

file name	DOI
all video files	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1116330
all photographs	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1116332